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Leadership style as an important factor in effective management: A study of Television Continental (TVC) Lagos, Nigeria

Kofoworola Adiat Raji ¹, Marian Olayemi Adeyemi ², Temitope Oladunni Alao ³ and Oshireku Vincent Onivefu ^{4,*}

¹ Internal Control Department, Kuda Microfinance Bank, Lagos, Nigeria.

² Department of Human Resource Management, Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom.

³ Department of Financial Analytics, Swansea University, Wales, United Kingdom.

⁴ Department of Business Development, Sterling Bank Plc, Lagos, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study investigates the critical role of leadership styles in effective management, with a specific focus on Television Continental (TVC) in Lagos, Nigeria. Leadership and management, though often used interchangeably, serve distinct functions within organizations. Leadership emphasizes influencing and motivating employees, while management focuses on planning, organizing, and coordinating resources to achieve organizational goals. Effective leadership is a cornerstone of successful management, as it fosters an environment where employees can excel and contribute to organizational objectives. The research addresses the problem of ineffective leadership styles in organizations, particularly in the media industry, where improper leadership approaches can demotivate employees and hinder goal attainment. The study aims to explore the relationship between leadership styles and employee performance, the accomplishment of organizational goals, and effective management. It also seeks to identify which leadership style best motivates employees. Using a descriptive survey design, data was collected from 70 employees at TVC through structured questionnaires. The study employed chi-square analysis to test hypotheses, revealing significant relationships between leadership styles and employee performance, goal accomplishment, and effective management. Findings indicate that democratic leadership is the most preferred and effective style for motivating employees, while autocratic and laissez-faire styles were less favored. The study concludes that effective management requires adaptable leadership styles tailored to specific situations. While democratic leadership fosters employee motivation and engagement, other styles may be necessary in different contexts. The research recommends that leaders be flexible in their approach, undergo leadership training, and be held accountable for their stewardship to enhance organizational effectiveness. This research contributes to the understanding of leadership dynamics in the media industry and provides practical insights for improving management practices through effective leadership styles.

Keywords: Leadership Styles; Effective Management; Employee Performance; Organizational Goals; Democratic Leadership; Motivation; Transformational Leadership

1. Introduction

The difference between leadership and management is a question that has been asked and answered in different ways. The biggest difference between leaders and managers is the way they motivate the people who work or follow them, and this sets the tone for most other aspects of what they do. Leaders manage and managers lead, but the two activities are not synonymous. Although, leadership and management are terms that are often considered synonymous. It is essential to understand that leadership is an essential part of effective management. Management functions can potentially provide leadership; leadership activities can contribute to managing. Nevertheless, some managers do not lead, and some leaders do not manage. As a crucial component of management, remarkable leadership behaviour

* Corresponding author: Oshireku Vincent Onivefu

stresses upon building an environment in which each and every employee develops and excels. Leadership is defined as the potential to influence and drive the group efforts towards the accomplishment of goals. This influence may originate from formal sources, such as that provided by acquisition of managerial position in an organization. Management is the act of getting people together to accomplish desired goals and objectives using available resources efficiently and effectively. Leadership is also described as the process of social influence in which one person can enlist the aid and support of others in the accomplishment of a common task. Leadership is also defined as the potential to influence and drive the group efforts towards the accomplishment of goals. This influence may originate from formal sources, such as that provided by acquisition of managerial position in an organization (Andrew,1995).

Developing effective management skills to deal with specific challenges and problems of each organization is the urgent needs of many businesses and organizations in the global competitive environment and rapid changing of technology. Globalization and rapidly developing technology show we are in a period of intense competition. Proper management is vital in these complex environments. The quality of manager and effective management styles can determine the culture of the organization, the productivity of its staff, and, ultimately, success or failure. A manager should have the ability to direct, supervise, encourage, inspire, and co-ordinate, and in doing so facilitate action and guide change. Managers develop their own leadership qualities and those of others. Management utilizes planning, organizational and communications skills. These skills are important in leadership also, but even more so are qualities such as integrity, honesty, courage, commitment, sincerity, passion, determination, compassion and sensitivity.

A manager must have traits of a leader, that is, he must possess leadership qualities. Leaders develop and begin strategies that build and sustain competitive advantage. Organizations require robust leadership and robust management for optimal organizational efficiency. Not all leaders possess the same attitude or same perspective. A few leaders adopt the carrot approach, and a few adopt the stick approach. That is, the use of rewards or punishments. Thus, all of the leaders do not get the things done in the same manner. Leadership styles, in managerial context, are the general ways a leader behaves towards subordinates to attain given objectives. The degree to which a manager delegates authority, the modes of power a manager employs and his relative concerns for human relationships or task orientation tend to reflect the manager's leadership style.

Each organization is a unique combination of individuals, tasks and objectives. Each manager has a unique personality and set of abilities. Thus, leadership is not set of permanent qualities enabling one person to suit best all occasions. For a good leader in one situation may be worse in another (Kurfi, 2009).

1.1. Statement of the problem

In many organizations, leaders who are responsible for managing their subordinates and activities within the organization use various leadership styles which may mar the accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives.

A lot of managers do not understand the importance of their leadership styles as a way to manage subordinates effectively. In an industry like the television media industry, many employees have to report to different leaders before the final implementation or execution of various tasks. This is because programmes are transmitted to viewers and errors are not tolerated. In the quest for proper output, the leaders use some improper leadership style to lead, and this could lead to lack of motivation in the follower. Managers and business owners employ one of many different types of leadership styles. Leadership does not always come in the same package with all leaders. Leadership is an essential aspect of management. Depending on which type of leadership style used, there could be some disadvantages associated with it. There has been a definite shift of focus from management to leadership in the context of business organizations. This shift can be attributed to the need of organizations to sustain their growth in the face of the rapidly changing competitive landscape across the industries. Not all leaders possess the same attitude or same perspective. Few leaders adopt the carrot approach, and a few adopt the stick approach. Thus, all of the leaders do not get the things done in the same manner. Their style varies. The leadership style varies with the kind of people the leader interacts and deals with. Accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives depends largely on effective teamwork by members of the organization. This includes managers and subordinates. The leadership style of managers towards subordinates determines how motivated he or she would be and the performance levels of these subordinates. Lack of understanding the various leadership styles and their effects is a major problem which needs to be solved so as to accomplish organizational goals.

1.2. Purpose/ objectives of study

The general objective of the study is to examine the importance of leadership styles in effective management in the Television Industry; a case study of Television Continental(TVC). More specifically, the objective is an attempt :

- To examine if there is any significant relationship between leadership styles and employees' performance.
- To ascertain if there is a significant relationship between leadership style and accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives.
- To examine if there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management.
- To ascertain which leadership style motivates employees to work better.

1.3. Research questions

- Is there any significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance?
- Is there a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives?
- Is there a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management?
- Is there any leadership style that motivates employees to work better?

1.4. Significance of the study

Learning leadership styles in management is vital for managers and aspiring managers because efficient business management always leads to business success. Another result of practicing the best management techniques is the great work or office environment that leads employees to always work with pleasure and motivation. Any organization's success depends upon the leadership style. A well-chosen leadership style will bring proper accomplishment of goals and objectives. It helps us to understand human behaviour in a wider perspective. It also helps in developing positive self-awareness. Leadership is an important function of management which helps to maximize efficiency and to achieve organizational goals. Understanding the importance of leadership is the key to business success. Leadership has so much influence on lives because so often it determines whether a particular activity is enjoyed. Since majority of days is spent participating in some event influenced by a coach, teacher, or other leader, the person in charge has a significant impact on the experience. Leadership is about building teams and communicating so that everyone works together. The importance of leadership is a key ingredient to successful businesses and championship teams. Teams that have this synergy tend to be the ones on top.

1.5. Hypotheses

- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance.
- H1: There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance.
- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives.
- H1: There a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives.
- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management.
- H1: There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective managements

1.6. Scope and limitation of the study

The write up seeks to study the various leadership styles and their effects in attaining set organizational goals. The study is limited to the staff/employees of Television Continental in Lagos state.

1.7. Operational definition of terms

- Leadership: is the process of social influence in which one person can enlist the aid and support of others in the accomplishment of a common task.
- Leadership style: is the manner and approach of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people.
- Management: is the act of getting people together to accomplish desired goals and objectives using available resources efficiently and effectively.
- Television Continental (TVC): Television Continental is a television station under the umbrella of Continental Broadcasting Services Lagos. TV Continental (formerly GOTEL TV-UHF65) is on Channel 49 on the UHF frequency and on Channel 21 on HITV satellite. The objective of TVC is to satisfy Nigeria's desire and quest for knowledge and information through high quality and exclusive news and entertainment.

The television station has the director of technical operations who oversees the control rooms and engineering departments. The deputy director's TV services and deputy director productions report to him. The head of operations,

head of engineering department, head of content acquisition and head of traffic/library report to the deputy director of productions. Operation officers in the master control room(MCR) and production control room(PCR) units report to the head of operations. The deputy director TV services oversee the TV related activities. The head of content acquisition previews all programmes before being shown on tv. The head of traffic / library previews independent programmes. The PCR unit deal with life programme while the MCR unit transmit programmes.

2. Literature review

2.1. Leadership and Management

Leadership and management are terms often used interchangeably. Management is more usually viewed as getting things done through other people to achieve stated organizational objectives. Management is regarded as relating to people working within a structured organization and with prescribed roles. The emphasis of leadership is on interpersonal behaviour. It is often associated with the willing and enthusiastic behaviour of followers. Leadership does not necessarily take place within the hierarchical structure of the organization (Mullins, 2007).

Today's leaders face the challenge of recruiting and holding on to competent employees in organizations. A leader's ability to inspire, motivate and create commitment to common goal is crucial (Bass, 1997). Leadership is less about personal needs, and more about the needs of the people and the organization being led. Leadership styles are not something to be tried on like so many suits, to see which fits. Rather, they should be adapted to the particular demands of the situation, the particular requirements of the people involved and the particular challenges facing the organization.

Certain styles tend to work well under some circumstances but are contraindicated in others. Some styles may have excellent short-term effects while being counterproductive in the long term.

Effective leadership in the change management process is particularly important because of all the factors involved in organizational change. As situations shift, leaders must be able to adapt and motivate employees to reduce fear, uncertainty and loss of employee morale. Anytime an organization goes through major changes, using the most effective leadership style can directly impact the success of the change and impact to the organization (Robert and Angelo,2004)

2.2. Leadership styles

Leadership style is the manner and approach of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. Kurt Lewin (1939) led a group of researchers to identify different styles of leadership. This early study has been very influential and established three major leadership styles. The three major styles of leadership are (U.S. Army Handbook, 1973):

- Authoritarian or autocratic
- Participative or democratic
- Delegative or Free Reign

Although good leaders use all three styles, with one of them normally dominant, bad leaders tend to stick with one style.

- Authoritarian/Autocratic: The tone is usually in form of "I want both of you to. . ."

This style is used when leaders tell their employees what they want done and how they want it accomplished, without getting the advice of their followers. Some of the appropriate conditions to use it is when all the information to solve the problem is available, the leader is short on time, and the employees are well motivated.

Some people tend to think of this style as a vehicle for yelling, using demeaning language, and leading by threats and abusing their power. This is not the authoritarian style, rather it is an abusive, unprofessional style called "bossing people around." It has no place in a leader's repertoire.

- Participative/Democratic: The tone is "Let's work together to solve this. . ."

This style involves the leader including one or more employees in the decision-making process, that is, determining what to do and how to do it. However, the leader maintains the final decision-making authority. Using this style is not a sign of weakness, rather it is a sign of strength that employees will respect. This is normally used when a part of the information is available, and the employees have other parts. A leader is not expected to know everything, and this is why it is necessary to employ knowledgeable and skillful employees. Using this style is of mutual benefit allows them to become part of the team and allows the leader to make better decisions.

- Delegation/Free reign: The tone is “You two take care of the problem while I go. . .”

In this style, the leader allows the employees to make the decisions. However, the leader is still responsible for the decisions that are made. This is used when employees are able to analyze the situation and determine what needs to be done and how to do it. This is also known as *laissez faire* or *laisse faire*, which is the non-interference in the affairs of others.

A good leader uses all three styles, depending on what forces are involved between the followers, the leader, and the situation. Some examples include:

- Using an authoritarian style on a new employee who is just learning the job. The leader is competent and a good coach. The employee is motivated to learn a new skill. The situation is a new environment for the employee.
- Using a participative style with a team of workers who know their job. The leader knows the problem, but does not have all the information. The employees know their jobs and want to become part of the team.
- Using a delegative style with a worker who knows more about the job than the leader. The leader cannot do everything, and the employee needs to take ownership of the job. In addition, this allows the leader to be at other places, doing other things.
- Using all three: Telling the employees that a procedure is not working correctly, and a new one must be established (authoritarian). Asking for their ideas and input on creating a new procedure (participative). Delegating tasks in order to implement the new procedure (delegative).

2.3. Primal leadership styles

Goleman's model of leadership is a relatively recent addition to the pantheon of leadership style. Daniel Goleman, a psychologist, was one of the major people who popularized Emotional Intelligence and then followed it up with a book called "Primal Leadership". It is based on the application of emotional intelligence to leadership. The six leadership styles are: coaching, pace setting, democratic, affiliative, authoritative and coercive. The most effective leaders can move among these styles, adopting the one that meets the needs of the moment. They can all become part of the leader's repertoire (Johannsen, 2010).

- **COACHING:** The Coach rests success on development of subordinates' and his or her own capabilities. Coaching leaders help employees identify their unique strengths and weaknesses and tie them to their personal and career aspirations. They make agreements with their employees about their role and responsibilities in enacting development plans, and they give plentiful instruction and feedback (Goleman, 2000). Coaches are good at delegating, building skills by varying staff's assignments, and tolerate short-term failure in the interest of long-term learning. Goals and expectations may not be clearly set; rather the Coach encourages subordinates to set their own goals and develop their own work plans. While the Coach's expectations tend to be high, the Coach may have difficulty communicating expectations or motivating through inspiration, but results tend to improve due to the highly positive effects on climate and staff competence and knowledge. The ongoing dialogue with the Coaching leader keeps staff informed of the direction in which the organization is moving, and the role the staff members' job plays in reaching objectives. Staff often respond to the Coaching style with high commitment.
- **PACESETTER/CHARISMATIC:** Pacesetters are star performers who lay sole claim to the limelight and seek it as a core goal. A Pacesetter would rather do a job himself or herself and is so good at what he or she does that he or she is reluctant to delegate. Leadership is achieved through setting an example, rather than through instruction or intentional staff development, establishment of high standards, and through imparting enthusiasm. People follow the Pacesetter because of who he or she is and/or what he or she can do, rather than because of his/her leadership skill. The Pacesetter tends to become coercive when a subordinate fails to live up to expectations or when there is trouble.
- **DEMOCRATIC/PARTICIPATIVE:** A Democratic leader “believes in” people and relies on the functioning of a group or team to achieve results. Subordinates take part in the decision-making process, and decisions result from a group consensus. There are frequent meetings, and subordinates are listened to by the leader. The style tends to foster responsibility, flexibility, and high morale. Because staff are engaged in decision making and planning, there is a tendency for them to be more realistic about what is and is not possible. The Democratic leader considers close supervision unnecessary after trust has been established, and negative feedback is offered sparingly.

- **AFFILIATIVE:** An Affiliator's primary concern is the well-being of his/her workforce and, probably, his/her own popularity. Task outcome may even be placed at a lower level of priority to that of subordinates' job satisfaction. This style can inspire deep loyalty within the work group. It can also foster free, open communication that inspires trust, a free flow of ideas, innovation, and risk taking. The Affiliator's positive feedback for accomplishment gives subordinates a great sense of having been recognized, which is excellent motivation for even greater achievement. The Affiliator may not give clear directions or set specific goals. He or she may avoid hard discussions that can cause bad feelings and may reward personal characteristics rather than job performance and attainment of outcomes. Affiliators can become serious negative factors in the work situation if their inaction takes them into the Laissez-Faire style. Most highly Affiliative leaders need to learn to use some skills of the Task-Oriented or Authoritative styles to ensure that their organization remains productive and on track.
- **AUTHORITARIAN/AUTHORITATIVE:** Central to the operation of the Authoritarian's style is the leader's responsibility for outcomes. While some input is sought from subordinates, the leader regards his/her influence as the key element in any major decision or job outcome. The Authoritative leader accomplishes ends through imparting a clear, compelling vision, sees to it that the vision is built into strategic planning, and that it guides action throughout the organization. The Authoritarian provides clear directions, monitors progress closely, and convinces subordinates of the position he or she wishes them to adopt by explaining why certain things are expected, done, or required and how individual actions fit into the larger picture. The feedback an Authoritarian offer may be positive or negative but clear, and the treatment of subordinates tends to be firm but fair. It may shade over into a Directive style when subordinates are given very little power or decision-making authority.
- **COERCIVE:** The fundamental element of the Coercer's leadership style is control – control of jobs, of rewards, and of people's actions to the extent the Coercer can achieve it. Results are obtained through direct, explicit instructions on expectations of a job and how the work is to be performed. This style of leadership demands obedience and requires a good deal of reporting back to the leader. Negative, personalized feedback and punishment or threats of discipline are the most common methods the Coercer uses to achieve results.

2.4. Other leadership styles

- **TASK-ORIENTED:** Getting a job done dominates the concern of this kind of leader, to the complete exclusion of other concerns, such as subordinates' satisfaction or well-being. The job outcome is what matters, and the leader may employ authoritarian, coercive, or democratic means to achieve that end. The Task-oriented leader actively defines structure, the work to be done, and the roles of subordinates in getting it accomplished. Task-oriented leaders put structures in place, plan, organize, and monitor. If the Task-Oriented leader is to be effective over an extended period, it is probably necessary for him/her to learn to employ skills embodied in the Affiliative and/or Democratic styles in order to sustain motivation and retain staff (Fernando, 2006).
- **BUREAUCRATIC:** Bureaucrat leadership may be like Authoritarian, although what is central are rules. The Bureaucrat operates "by the book" and requires subordinates to follow procedures and rules to the letter. If rules and regulations do not cover a situation, the Bureaucratic leader looks to superiors for guidance. The style can be effective if staff must repeat the same tasks over and over, are required to fully understand procedures and standards, are working with dangerous or delicate equipment, or are engaged in situations that involve significant hazard to themselves or the public. The means of achieving staff compliance with rules may be borrowed from the Coercive through the Affiliative or Democratic styles. The Bureaucratic style has negative effects on flexibility, initiative, relationships between staff, and motivation. However, it also provides consistency of approach.
- **LAISSEZ-FAIRE:** It is difficult to think of a Laissez-Faire leader as a leader, since his/her objective is to avoid influencing subordinates. Thus, subordinates have a great deal of autonomy and authority. The Laissez-Faire style of leadership can lead to organizational ineffectiveness if there is, in addition, no control over processes or weak or absent organization. Desired outcomes may not be achieved if there is no systematic approach to problem solving. Individual goals and agendas can come to replace those of the organization or workgroup. However, under the right circumstances, such as when a workforce is highly educated, skilled, and experienced, and when the goals of the organization are clear to everyone, or when outside consultants are often used, the approach can foster creativity, independent thinking, and personal responsibility. Laissez-Faire may be the style of choice when the workforce is considerably more technically knowledgeable than the leader is.

- **EMPOWERING:** A new, possibly more effective kind of Laissez-Faire leadership is Empowering leadership which relies on delegation of responsibility to subordinates. When well-practiced, it is built on clear lines of authority, responsibility, and roles and well-developed structures for workflow and problem solving. This is a relatively new style and is used in American companies having autonomous, possibly geographically dispersed, divisions. A few younger Asian business leaders have adopted the Empowering style.
- **PEOPLE-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP OR RELATIONS-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP:** This is the opposite of task-oriented leadership. With people-oriented leadership, leaders are totally focused on organizing, supporting, and developing the people in their teams. It's a participative style, and it tends to encourage good teamwork and creative collaboration. In practice, most leaders use both task-oriented and people-oriented styles of leadership.
- **SERVANT LEADERSHIP:** This term, created by Robert Greenleaf in the 1970s, describes a leader who is often not formally recognized as such. When someone, at any level within an organization, leads simply by meeting the needs of the team, he or she is described as a "servant leader." In many ways, servant leadership is a form of democratic leadership, because the whole team tends to be involved in decision making. Supporters of the servant leadership model suggest that it's an important way to move ahead in a world where values are increasingly important, and where servant leaders achieve power on the basis of their values and ideals. Others believe that in competitive leadership situations, people who practice servant leadership can find themselves left behind by leaders using other leadership styles (Quinn, 2005).

2.5. The leadership methods

- **TRANSACTIONAL:** Transactional leadership cuts across the leadership styles described above. It is a method of leadership, as opposed to a true, personal leadership style. Its fundamental assumption is that subordinates work to receive compensation. Thus, Transactional leaders motivate through the use of contingent rewards or negative consequences. The Transactional leader's main focus is on setting goals and clarifying the relationship between performance and rewards. The leader tells his subordinates what they are to do to receive rewards. Constructive feedback is offered in terms of progress toward or away from rewards. This style of leadership starts with the idea that team members agree to obey their leader totally when they accept a job. The "transaction" is usually the organization paying the team members in return for their effort and compliance. The leader has a right to "punish" team members if their work doesn't meet the pre-determined standard. Team members can do little to improve their job satisfaction under transactional leadership. The leader could give team members some control of their income/reward by using incentives that encourage even higher standards or greater productivity. Alternatively, a transactional leader could practice "management by exception" – rather than rewarding better work, the leader could take corrective action if the required standards are not met. Transactional leadership is really a type of management, not a true leadership style, because the focus is on short-term tasks. It has serious limitations for knowledge-based or creative work; however, it can be effective in other situations. The Transactional leader can punish subordinates for performance that does not meet a pre-determined standard. Often it is assumed that a clear chain of command is necessary to achieve results and that the concentration of authority and power are at the top of the chain. It is assumed that subordinates agree to cede their own authority to the top leadership. Subordinates may have little opportunity to improve their job satisfaction or influence decision making, since there may not be any allowance for "managing up." When the Transactional leader allocates work to subordinates, they are fully responsible for it. The Transactional leader often uses management by exception, working on the principle that if something is operating to defined (and hence expected) performance, then it does not need attention. Exceptions to expectation require praise and reward for exceeding expectation, while some kind of corrective action is applied for performance below expectation. Some Transactional leaders only give attention to what does not meet performance standards. In some work, the functioning of the Transactional leader is associated with "management," and Transformational functioning is considered "leadership" (Tarplett, 2004).
- **TRANSFORMATIONAL:** Transformational leadership is also a method which cuts across leaders' styles. Transformational leaders assume that subordinates will follow a person who inspires them and that to inspire, the leader must be a person with vision and passion. They achieve this through being highly visible, in constant communication with their teams, and by infusing their actions and communications with enthusiasm and energy. Relationships are built between leadership and subordinates. Many Transformational leaders delegate freely and may rely upon the talent and expertise of members of their team to achieve results. They tend to give recognition of accomplishment. People with this leadership style are true leaders who inspire their teams constantly with a shared vision of the future. While this leader's enthusiasm is often passed onto the team, he

or she can need to be supported by "detail people." That's why, in many organizations, both transactional and transformational leadership are needed. The transactional leaders (or managers) ensure that routine work is done reliably, while the transformational leaders look after initiatives that add new value (Arthur, 2008). Since the success of the Transformational leader's organization depends upon his/her vision and the successful promotion of that vision among his/her subordinates, the leader must first perfect his vision of the future and must work on his/her own integrity and trustworthiness, because the leader is always selling him/herself as well as the vision, and flaws in him/herself will impact subordinates' buy-in to the total package. Cross-cultural research indicates that characteristics of the Transformational leader are recognized as "leadership" in many cultures around the world. Thus, independent of how effective a person is, he or she is more likely to be recognized as having leadership qualities if he/she exhibits aspects of the Transformational method (Tarplett,2004).

2.6. Factors that influence leadership styles

While the proper leadership style depends on the situation, there are factors that influence which leadership style to use:

- The manager's personal background. What personality, knowledge, values, ethics, and experiences the manager has. What he or she thinks will work.
- The employees being supervised. Employees are individuals with different personalities and backgrounds. The leadership style managers use will vary depending upon the individual employee and what he or she will respond best to.
- The company. The traditions, values, philosophy, and concerns of the company will influence how a manager acts.
- How much time is available.
- Whether relationships are based on respect and trust or on disrespect.
- Who has the information, the leader or the employees, or both.
- How well the employees are trained and how well you know the task.
- Internal conflicts.
- Stress levels.
- Type of task, structured, unstructured, complicated, or simple.

2.6.1. Use of Consideration and Structure in leadership styles

Two other approaches that leaders use are:

- Consideration (employee orientation):leaders are concerned about the human needs of their employees. They build teamwork, help employees with their problems, and provide psychological support.
- Structure (task orientation):leaders believe that they get results by consistently keeping people busy and urging them to produce.

There is evidence that leaders who are considerate in their leadership style are higher performers and are more satisfied with their job (Schriesheim, 1982).

2.7. Classification of leadership styles

According to Kurfi (2009), leadership styles are, generally, classified into three:

- Traditional Styles: The traditional styles of leadership are:
 - Autocratic leadership
 - Democratic leadership
 - Laissez-faire leadership
- Modern Styles: This is an alternative method brought up by Ransis Likert (1967):
 - Job-centred
 - Employees-centred
 - Job-employee centred
- Contingency Approach: These approaches are:
 - Fielder's Model
 - Path-Goal Model
 - Vroom- Yetton

2.8. The traditional styles of leadership

2.8.1. Autocratic leadership

Autocratic management leaders are highly authoritarian. He has enough power to impose his will on followers and does not hesitate to do so if necessary. This leader deliberately appeals to lower-level needs of subordinates on the assumption that is the level on which they operate. Douglas McGregor (1960) called the autocratic presumptions about followers through Theory X. According to Theory X:

- People inherently dislike work and when possible will avoid it.
- People have little ambition, tend to shun responsibility, and prefer to be directed.
- Above all, people want security.
- It is necessary to use coercion, control and threats of punishment to get people to work.

This leader centralizes authority and all little latitude in making decisions, he supervised work in close detail manner than in general form.

Benevolent autocrat: This is an autocrat that uses reward power to influence rather than coercive power. Though still an authoritarian leader, he shows active concern for the welfare of his subordinates, and allows participation in planning, though; he retains the actual power to make executive decisions.

2.8.2. Democratic leadership

This leader is labeled by Douglas McGregor (1960) as Theory Y leader. He believes that:

- Work is a natural phenomenon, and if the conditions are favorable people will not only accept responsibility, but they will also seek it.
- If people are committed to organizational objectives, they will exercise self-direction and self-control
- Commitment is a function of the rewards associated with goal attainment.
- The capacity for creativity in problem solving is widely distributed in the population, and the intellectual patents of the average human being are only partially utilized.

This leader uses a lot of influence, allows autonomy and avoids imposing his will on subordinates. Authority here is decentralized and subordinates participate in decision-making. He believes that people are motivated by higher-level needs for social interaction achievement and self-actualization: he tries to make subordinates' duties challenging.

2.8.3. Laissez-faire Leadership

This gives subordinates total freedom to select their own objectives and monitor their own work. True laissez-faire is in fact "non-leadership" because the leader has almost no influence over the group. This makes it difficult to distinguish the leader from the followers. This leadership style is probably a descriptive ideal that does not really exist.

2.9. Modern styles of leadership

According to Rensis Likert (1967), there are two alternative approaches to leadership styles in an organization: job-centred or employee-centred. Whereas Blake and Mouten (1964) proposed socio/technical style, which combines both job and people.

2.9.1. Job-centered Leaders

The Job-centered manager, referred to as task oriented, is primary concerned with the design of work and the development of rewards to increase productivity. The aim here is to get the maximum return to the manager or organization at least cost and probably at the highest cost to the worker.

2.9.2. Employee-centered Leaders

The concern here is people. The leader focuses on improving performance through improving human relations. He allows maximum participation in decision-making and avoids detail supervision. His behaviour is similar to that of the participative style leaders.

According to Likert (1967), management style could either be job-or employee-centered. But this is not true because, the best management/leadership style is that which combines both job and people, that is, socio/ technical style. That is, it is very possible for the manager to show great concern for the work as well as the people.

2.10. Contingency approach to effective leadership

The inability of earlier researchers to find a consistent relationship among leadership styles, satisfaction and productivity strongly indicates that some other factors (s) were at work. To find these factors, the theorists began to look beyond leader and followers and consider the situation as a whole.

There are three contingency models of leadership effectiveness as follows:

- Fiedler's (1978) model or approach
- Path-Goal model or approach
- Vroom-Yetton (1973) model

2.10.1. Fielder's Model

This model is based on the notion that successful leadership depends on a match between the leader, the situation and the subordinate. He suggests that there is no one best style. The effectiveness of a leader is determined by how well his style fits the situation. A manager can maintain this fit by:

- Understanding his-own leadership style.
- Analyzing the situation
- Matching the style to the situation either by planning himself in situation to which the style is suited or by altering a given situation so that it is compatible with the style.

2.10.2. Path-Goal Model

This model draws heavily on the expectancy theory of motivation. Expectancy theory holds that people will do what they expect will result in rewards they want. This is the basis of the Path-Goal. The theory proposes that leaders influence subordinates by clarifying what must be done (the path) to obtain rewards they want (the goal). According to House (1971), leaders can best help subordinates clarify what they should do (the path) to get the rewards they want (the goal) by adopting different leadership styles-directive, supportive, participative and achievement oriented-in different situations. These leadership styles are defined as follows:

- Directive behaviour: Leadership activities focus on scheduling work, establishing performance standards and clarifying expectations regarding employees' performance. This is very similar to Job-centred behavioural and initiating structure.
- Supportive behaviour: Leadership behaviour focuses on improving interpersonal relationships and being generally supportive, accessible and friendly. This is similar to employee centred behaviour. The leader allows subordinate participation. This model considers both behavior and situation factors in its analysis of appropriate leadership styles. So, leaders should select the leadership style that best fits the characteristics of the situation, the subordinate and the demands of their job.
- Participative behaviour: Leadership behaviour focuses on consulting with subordinates and taking their opinions and suggestions into account when making decisions.
- Achievement-oriented behaviour: Leadership activities focus on setting challenging goals, seeking improvements, emphasizing excellence in performance and showing confidence that subordinates will attain high standards.

2.10.3. Vroom-Yetton

The Vroom-Yetton (1973) leadership decision model as its name implies focuses on the decision-making process. According to this model there are five possible styles a manager can use to make a decision:

- You solve the problem or make the decision yourself, using information available to you at that time.
- You obtain necessary information from your subordinates then decide on the solution to the problem yourself.
- You share the problem with relevant subordinates individually, getting their ideas and suggestions without bringing them together as a group.
- You share the problem with your subordinates as a group collectively obtaining their ideas and suggestions, to solve the problem alone as a leader.
- You share the problem with your subordinates as a group together, you generate and evaluate alternatives and attempt to reach agreement on a solution. Your role is much of a chairing, and you also give your opinion before a collective decision on the matter is reached.

2.11. The interplay of leadership and management

Management comprises planning, organizing, staffing, leading or directing, and controlling an organization (a group of one or more people or entities) or effort for the purpose of accomplishing a goal.(Wikipedia, 2012). Leadership and management must go hand in hand. They are not the same thing. But they are necessarily linked, and complementary. Any effort to separate the two is likely to cause more problems than it solves. Still, much ink has been spent delineating the differences. The manager's job is to plan, organize and coordinate. The leader's job is to inspire and motivate (Alan, 2012). In spite of efforts made to understand leadership as distinct from management, leadership is also studied as an essential element of management along with planning, organizing, staffing and controlling. This view depicts leadership as an important function of management or to make it simpler, leadership is shown as an important managerial role. In this managerial function thrust is on creation of long-term vision, development of values, culture and behaviours necessary for pursuing the vision and inspiring people for voluntary commitment to organizational cause. And yet at the same time it is leadership, which is responsible for designing and developing a suitable management system for the organization, to ensure systematic and orderly accomplishment of desired goals.

A leader is one who influences the behavior and work of others in group efforts towards achievement of specified goals in a given situation. On the other hand, a manager can be a true manager only if he has got traits of leader in him. Manager at all levels are expected to be the leaders of work groups so that subordinates willingly carry instructions and accept their guidance. Leadership and managership are two synonymous terms” are an incorrect statement. Leadership doesn't require any managerial position to act as a leader. On the other hand, a manager can be a true manager only if he has got the traits of leader in him. By virtue of his position, the manager has to provide leadership to his group. A manager has to perform all five functions to achieve goals, i.e., Planning, Organizing, Staffing, Directing, and Controlling. Leadership is a part of these functions. Leadership as a general term is not related to managership. A person can be a leader by virtue of qualities in him. For example: leader of a club, class, welfare association, social organization, etc. Therefore, it is true to say that “All managers are leaders, but all leaders are not managers” (MSG, 2012).

The importance of leadership in organization emerges from its role of creating and shaping organizational culture and setting a progressive direction for the organization. Without this there is no role for management, no cause for it to exist. Leadership creates a context for the management to exist. Management on the other hand, through well laid out processes and systems, ensures that effective leadership at every level is developed in the organization, as a driver for future growth. Leaders create the future through strong ideas and leave strong imprints of ideology for the company on which the management system is designed. When executives are involved in the functions of planning, organizing, staffing and controlling they are said to be managing. When they are involved in influencing people through inspirational words and actions for achieving the collective goals they are said to be leading. Leadership is about looking, thinking and bringing change in the organization, whereas management is about ensuring order and consistency in the organization. In the absence of leadership, management is a stifling bureaucracy and devoid of clear ends (vision, mission or long-term goals) and means (values and behaviours required in the long term). Also, leadership without effective management may lack the discipline and coordinated effort to accomplish long term goals of the company. Leadership is still in art form, where there is no best or worst way of doing it – no universal framework or models exist. On the other hand, management is treated as science, where definite frameworks and systems exist to carry out the functions of planning, organizing, staffing and controlling. An organization is run on the strength of its management systems while leadership provides the vigour to look beyond and gallop ahead. Hence, leadership and management may be considered two inseparable and intertwined aspects of organizational reality, without one the effectiveness of other is jeopardised (Alagse, 2012).

3. Research methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter is designed to present how the study was carried out. To this end, the chapter consists of the following sub-headings: research design, population of the study, instrumentation, data collection and procedure, problems encountered during data collection, methods of data analyses.

This study was guided by descriptive survey design to establish the relationship between variables involving the relationship between employee performance and leadership styles in effective management. The study was carried out in a media house: Television Continental (TVC) Lagos State.

3.2. Research design

The survey method was used for the study. This type of research design describes the variables, that is, dependent and independent under study. The independent variable is leadership style, and the dependent variable is effective management. It allows generalization to be made from large population when representative samples are drawn.

3.3. Sample size and sampling techniques

The study used the probability of sampling, and it is further categorized into simple random sampling. The sampling technique used was stratified and simple random sampling technique. This technique allows every member of the population an equal chance of being represented in the sample. And also, various shades of opinion are accommodated for balanced view.

The sample size of this study comprised sixty (70) employees ranging from top management to lower-level management. Sample is based on the total population and this sample size covers the organization.

3.4. Description of study population

The population for the study consisted of seventy (70) employees of Television Continental media house Lagos State. The population size consists of management that is responsible for steering the organization toward the right direction in the attainment of its goal and objectives, senior staff who head and supervise the various departments in the organization and junior staff who serve as clerks and support staff.

3.5. Instrumentation: validity and reliability

The primary instrument used for the collection of data was constructed questionnaire using 5-point Likert scale (that is: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree). The questionnaire contained 26 items relating to the variables under study. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section A consists of biodata of respondents while Section B consists of various statements relating to leadership style and effective management. The research instrument was administered to seventy respondents ranging from top management level to lower-level workers.

Table 1 Questionnaire Response Rate

Response	Frequency	Percent (%)
Returned	70	87.5
Unreturned	10	12.5
Total	80	100

Source: Field Survey, 2012

Table 1 shows that out of 80 copies of questionnaires distributed to respondents, 70 were fully completed and returned, representing 87.5% while 10 copies of questionnaires were unreturned representing 12.5%. Thus, majority of the respondents completed and returned the questionnaires.

3.6. Data collection procedure

The data used for the study was collected from two sources, namely primary and secondary sources. Primary sources of data collection: these include the use of questionnaires to obtain first-hand information. Secondary sources of data collection: these include textbooks, publications, journals and articles written by various authors relating to the topic under study.

3.7. Problems encountered during collection of data

The study used both primary and secondary data in carrying out this research. However, there were some barriers to getting the data needed for the study to be effectively carried out. In the collection of the primary data, which was done using the questionnaire method, some of the challenges encountered include: the loss of questionnaires distributed, unreturned questionnaires, incompletely filled questionnaires by respondents, delay of respondents to respond to the distributed questionnaires thereby causing delay in the research process. There were also challenges of gaining access to the organization and unwillingness of employees to accept questionnaires. The challenges of secondary data using journals, books and internet include inaccessibility of materials, cost implications of getting journals, poor electric power supply and poor internet services which all affected the execution of the research work.

3.8. Methods of data analyses

The data for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency table and percentage method. The formulated hypotheses were tested using chi-square (χ^2) analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS)

4. Presentation, analyses and interpretation of data

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the statistical analyses and findings with particular reference to the hypotheses which were tested using chi-square test at 0.05 significance levels by using the Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS vs. 17).

4.2. Analyses of respondents' biodata

Table 2 Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
	Female	40	57.1	57.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

This table shows that 42.9% of the respondents are males, while 57.1% are females. This analysis makes it clear that females are more than males in the sample used.

Table 3 Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	10	14.3	14.3	14.3
	25-30	40	57.1	57.1	71.4
	31-40	15	21.4	21.4	92.9
	51 yrs and above	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table reveals that 14.3% of the respondents are within the age range of 18-24 years, 57.1% within 25-30 years, 21.4% 31-40, while 7.1% are within 51 years and above. This shows that majority of the respondent are in their late 20s.

Table 4 Academic Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SSCE	10	14.3	14.3	14.3
	OND	25	35.7	35.7	50.0
	HND/BSC	25	35.7	35.7	85.7
	MSc/MBA	5	7.1	7.1	92.9
	PHD	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

From the above table, 14.3% of the respondents are SSCE holders, 35.7% are OND and HND or BSC holders, while 7.1% are both MSc/MBA and PhD holders. This shows that many of the respondents are graduates of tertiary institutions.

Table 5 Marital Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
	Married	40	57.1	57.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table shows that 42.9% of the respondents are single, while 57.1% are married. Hence, the analysis reveals that majority of the respondents are married.

4.3. Analyses of respondents to research questions

Table 6 Employees need to be supervised closely, or they are not likely to do their work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	28.6	28.6	28.6
	Agree	25	35.7	35.7	64.3
	Neutral	10	14.3	14.3	78.6
	Disagree	10	14.3	14.3	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

From the above table, 28.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees need to be supervised closely, or they are not likely to do their work, while 35.7% agreed, 14.3% are neutral, 14.3% disagreed, and 7.1% strongly disagreed. This shows that employees need to be supervised closely indeed, or they are not likely to do their work, since many of the respondents agreed.

Table 7 Employees want to be part of the decision-making process

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	50	71.4	71.4	71.4
	Agree	10	14.3	14.3	85.7
	Neutral	10	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

71.4% of the respondents from the table above strongly agreed that employees want to be part of the decision-making process, while 14.3% agreed, and 14.3% are neutral. Hence, employees want to be part of the decision-making process, since majority of the respondents agreed.

Table 8 In complex situations, leaders should let subordinates work problems out on their own

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	15	21.4	21.4	21.4
	Agree	5	7.1	7.1	28.5
	Neutral	20	28.6	28.6	57.1
	Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	78.6
	Strongly Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table reveals that 21.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that in complex situations, leaders should let subordinates work problems out on their own, while 7.1% agreed, 28.6% are neutral, while 21.4% both disagreed and strongly disagreed. It can be inferred from the above analysis that in complex situations, leaders should not let subordinates work problems out on their own. Since many disagreed.

Table 9 It is fair to say that most employees in the general population are lazy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	10	14.3	14.3	14.3
	Agree	15	21.4	21.4	35.7
	Neutral	10	14.3	14.3	50.0
	Disagree	20	28.6	28.6	78.6
	Strongly Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table reveals that 14.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that it is fair to say that most employees in the general population are lazy, while 21.4% agreed, 14.3% are neutral, 28.6% disagreed, while 21.4% strongly disagreed. Hence, from the above analysis it is not fair to say that most employees in the general population are lazy

Table 10 Providing guidance without pressure is the key to being a good leader

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	35	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	10	14.3	14.3	64.3
	Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	85.7
	Strongly Disagree	10	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table shows that 50% of the respondents strongly agreed that providing guidance without pressure is the key to being a good leader, while 14.3% agreed, 21.4% disagreed, and 14.3% strongly disagreed. It can therefore be concluded from the above table that providing guidance without pressure is really the key to being a good leader.

Table 11 Leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	20	28.6	28.6	28.6
	Neutral	20	28.6	28.6	57.2
	Disagree	25	35.7	35.7	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

Table 11 above reveals that 28.6% of the respondents agreed that leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work, while 28.6% are neutral, 35.7% disagreed, and 7.1% strongly disagreed. This shows that leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work, since many agreed.

Table 12 As a rule, employees must be giving rewards or punishments in order to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
	Agree	20	28.6	28.6	71.5
	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	78.6
	Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The above table reveals that 42.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that as a rule, employees must be giving rewards or punishments in order to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives, while 28.6% agreed, 7.1% are neutral, and 21.4% disagreed. This shows that as a rule, employees must be giving rewards or punishments in order to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives, since many agreed.

Table 13 Most workers want frequent and supportive communication from their leaders

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	65	92.9	92.9	92.9
	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 92.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that most workers want frequent and supportive communication from their leaders, while 7.1% are neutral. This analysis shows that most workers want frequent and supportive communication from their leaders.

Table 14 There is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	55	78.6	78.6	78.6
	Agree	10	14.3	14.3	92.9
	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 78.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance, while 14.3% agreed, and 7.1% are neutral. This analysis shows that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance.

Table 15 As a rule, leaders should allow subordinates to appraise their own work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	5	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Agree	25	35.7	35.7	42.9
	Neutral	30	42.9	42.9	85.7
	Disagree	10	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 7.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that as a rule, leaders should allow subordinates to appraise their own work, while 35.7% agreed, 42.9% are neutral, and 14.3% disagreed. It can be inferred from this table that as a rule, leaders may or may not allow subordinates to appraise their own work. Since many are neutral.

Table 16 Most employees feel insecure about their work and need direction

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	16	22.9	22.9	22.9
	Agree	15	21.4	21.4	44.3
	Neutral	20	28.6	28.6	72.9
	Disagree	14	20.0	20.0	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Table 16 shows a cumulative percentage of 44.3% of the respondents agreed that most employees feel insecure about their work and need direction while 55.7% of the respondents did not agree to this.

Table 17 Leaders need to help subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	25	35.7	35.7	35.7
	Agree	45	64.3	64.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

Table 17 above shows that 100% of the respondents cumulatively agreed that leaders need to help subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work. This analysis shows that leaders really need to help subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work, since all the respondents agreed.

Table 18 Leaders should give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	50	71.4	71.4	78.6
	Strongly Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

Table 18 above reveals that 7.1% of the respondents are neutral whether leaders should give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own or not, while 71.4% disagreed, and 21.4% strongly disagreed. This means leaders should not give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own. Since many disagreed.

Table 19 The leader is the chief judge of the achievements of the members of the group

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	25	35.7	35.7	35.7
	Agree	15	21.4	21.4	57.1
	Neutral	15	21.4	21.4	78.6
	Disagree	10	14.3	14.3	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

Table 19 above reveals that 35.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that the leader is the chief judge of the achievements of the members of the group, while 21.4% agreed, 21.4% are neutral, 14.3% disagreed, and 7.1% strongly disagreed. It can be concluded that the leader is really the chief judge of the achievements of the members of the group.

Table 20 It is the leader's job to help subordinates find their "passion"

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	28.6	28.6	28.6
	Agree	10	14.3	14.3	42.9
	Neutral	30	42.9	42.9	85.7
	Disagree	10	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 28.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that it is the leader's job to help subordinates find their passion, while 14.3% agreed, 42.9% are neutral, and 14.3% disagreed. It can be established from this analysis that it is the leader's job to help subordinates find their "passion".

Table 21 In most situations, workers prefer little input from the leader

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	28.6	28.6	28.6
	Agree	20	28.6	28.6	57.1
	Neutral	10	14.3	14.3	71.4
	Disagree	20	28.6	28.6	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 57.1% of the respondents cumulatively agreed that in most situations, workers prefer little input from the leader, while 14.3% are neutral, and 28.6% disagreed. Hence, the analysis shows that in most situations, workers indeed prefer little input from the leader.

Table 22 Effective leaders give orders and clarify procedures

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	55	78.6	78.6	78.6
	Agree	5	7.1	7.1	85.7
	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 78.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that effective leaders give orders and clarify procedures, while 7.1% agreed, 7.1% are neutral, and 7.1% strongly disagreed. This shows that effective leaders give orders and clarify procedures, since majority of the respondents agreed.

Table 23 There is significant relationship between leadership styles and effective managements

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	40	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	20	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	5	7.1	7.1	92.9
	Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

The table above shows that 57.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management, while 28.6% agreed, 7.1% are neutral, and 7.1% disagreed. It can be inferred from this table that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective managements, since majority of the respondents agreed.

Table 24 People are basically competent and if given a task they will do a good job

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	28.6	28.6	28.6
	Neutral	30	42.9	42.9	71.4
	Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	78.6
	Strongly Disagree	15	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

From the table above 28.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that people are basically competent and if given a task will do a good job, while 42.9% are neutral, 7.1% disagreed, and 21.4% strongly disagreed. This shows that people are basically not competent and if given a task will not do a good job, since majority of the respondents disagreed.

Table 25 In general, it is best to leave subordinates alone

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	5	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Disagree	40	57.1	57.1	64.3
	Strongly Disagree	25	35.7	35.7	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

From the table above 7.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that in general, it is best to leave subordinates alone, 57.1% disagreed, and 35.7% strongly disagreed. This shows that in general, it is not a good idea to leave subordinates alone, since majority of the respondents disagreed.

Table 26 There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	50	71.4	71.4	71.4
	Neutral	10	14.3	14.3	85.7
	Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	92.9
	Strongly Disagree	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, July 2012

From the table above 71.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives, while 14.3% are neutral, and 7.1% both disagreed and strongly disagreed. This shows that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives, since majority of the respondents agreed.

4.4. Testing of hypotheses

4.4.1. Hypothesis 1

- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance
- H1: There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance

Table 27 Using Chi-Square

There is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Neutral	5	23.3	-18.3
Agree	10	23.3	-13.3
Strongly Agree	55	23.3	31.7
Total	70		

Test Statistics	
There is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance	
Chi-Square	65.000a
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 23.3.	

4.5. Interpretation of Results

The table above gives a chi-square value of 65.000 with 2 degrees of freedom and p-value of 0.000 which is considered less than 0.05. Hence we reject the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance and accept the alternative hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and employee performance.

4.5.1. Hypothesis 2

- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives
- H1: There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives

Table 28 Chi-Square Test

There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Disagree	5	17.5	-12.5
Disagree	5	17.5	-12.5
Neutral	10	17.5	-7.5
Strongly Agree	50	17.5	32.5
Total	70		

Table 29 Statistics Test

Test Statistics	
There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives	
Chi-Square	81.429a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 17.5.

4.6. Interpretation of Results

The table above gives a chi-square value of 81.429 with 3 degree of freedom and p-value of 0.000 which is considered less than 0.05. Hence we reject the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, we conclude that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and accomplishment of organizational goals/objectives.

4.6.1. Hypothesis 3

- H0: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management
- H1: There is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management

Table 30 Chi-Square Test

There is significant relationship between leadership styles and effective managements			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Disagree	5	17.5	-12.5
Neutral	5	17.5	-12.5
Agree	20	17.5	2.5
Strongly Agree	40	17.5	22.5
Total	70		

Test Statistics	
There is significant relationship between leadership styles and effective managements	
Chi-Square	47.143a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 17.5.

4.7. Interpretation of Results

The table above gives a chi-square value of 47.143 with 3 degrees of freedom and p-value of 0.000 which is considered less than 0.05. Hence we reject the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, we conclude that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management.

Table 31 Autocratic Leadership Style

Statements	Respondents				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Employees need to be supervised closely, otherwise they are not likely to do their work.	20	25	10	10	5
It is fair to say that most employees in the general population are lazy.	10	15	10	20	15
As a rule, employees must be given rewards or punishments in order to motivate them to achieve organizational objectives.	30	20	5	15	-
The leader is the chief judge of the achievements of the members of the group.	25	15	15	10	5
Most employees feel insecure about their work and need direction.	16	15	20	14	5
Effective leaders give orders and clarify procedures.	55	5	5	-	5
Total	156	95	65	69	35

Ratios	251	65	104
Percentages of respondents who agreed, disagreed or were neutral	59.8%	15.5%	24.7%

Table 32 Democratic Leadership Style

Statements	Respondents				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Employees want to be part of the decision-making process.	50	10	10	-	-
Providing guidance without pressure is the key to being a good leader.	35	10	-	15	10
Most workers want frequent and supportive communication from their leaders.	65	-	5	-	-
Leaders need to help subordinates accept responsibility for completing their work.	25	45	-	-	-
It is the leader’s job to help subordinates find their “passion.”	20	10	30	10	-
People are basically competent and if given a task will do a good job.	20	-	30	5	15
TOTAL	215	75	75	30	25
RATIOS	290	75	55		
PERCENTAGES OF RESPONDENTS WHO AGREED, DISAGREED OR WERE NEUTRAL	69.1%	13.1%	17.8%		

Table 33 Laissez Faire Leadership Style

STATEMENTS	RESPONDENTS				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
In complex situations, leaders should let subordinates work problems out on their own.	15	5	20	15	15
Leadership requires staying out of the way of subordinates as they do their work.	-	20	20	25	5
As a rule, leaders should allow subordinates to appraise their own work.	5	25	30	10	-
Leaders should give subordinates complete freedom to solve problems on their own.	-	-	5	50	15
In most situations, workers prefer little input from the leader	20	20	10	20	-
In general, it is best to leave subordinates alone.	5	-	-	40	25
TOTAL	45	70	85	160	60
RATIOS	115	85	220		
PERCENTAGES OF RESPONDENTS WHO AGREED, DISAGREED OR WERE NEUTRAL	27.4%	20.2%	52.4%		

Table 34 Respondents That Agreed to The Leadership Styles

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AUTOCRATIC STYLE	251	38.3	38.3	38.3
	DEMOCRATIC STYLE	290	44.2	44.2	82.5
	LAISSEZ FAIRE STYLE	115	17.5	17.5	100.0
	Total	656	100.0	100.0	

Table 29 shows that the leadership style with the highest percentage is the democratic leadership style where 38.3% agreed to autocratic style, 44.2% agreed to the democratic style while only 17.5% agreed to the laissez faire leadership style. This implies that the laissez faire style is the least desirable leadership style while the democratic leadership style is most preferred by the respondents.

Figure 1 Bar Chart Showing Respondents that Agreed to the Leadership Styles

Figure 2 Pie Chart Showing the Number Of Respondents That Agreed To Authoritative, Democratic Or Laissez Fairre Leadership Style

5. Summary

5.1. Introduction

In this research work, an attempt has been made to analyze the various leadership styles and their effects and importance in effective management in a media house. Discussions, summary, conclusions and recommendations drawn from the findings of this research work were made in this chapter.

5.2. Discussion And Summary of Findings

Leadership is an important element of management which is usually expressed in terms of leadership styles. As explained in chapter one, Television Continental is an organization in the television media industry. The CEO is the head in the organizational chart, who is being reported to by directors in various departments. The heads of the various departments also report to these directors while employees in various units under these departments report to the heads of departments. For example, the operations officers in the Master Control Room(MCR) and Production Control Room(PCR) units are led by the head of operations, who concurrently is also being led by the deputy director of production who reports to the director of technical operations. This shows that there is a long chain of leaders and subordinates in the organization. Each of these leaders use different leadership styles when working with their subordinates and this could affect effective management in the organization. There are various leadership styles and these have been discussed in this study as shown in chapter two.

Transactional and transformational leadership styles are methods of leadership which cut across all leadership styles. Transactional leaders use disciplinary power and an array of incentives to motivate employees to perform at their best. Transformational leadership styles focus on team-building, motivation and collaboration with employees at different levels of an organization to accomplish change for the better. Various leadership styles were discussed in chapter two. These include bureaucratic, charismatic, participative/democratic, autocratic, delegative, laissez faire, servant, task-oriented and so on. These leadership styles were explained in details.

The objective of this study as stated in the earlier part was to examine the significant relationship between :

- leadership styles and employees' performance
- leadership style and accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives
- leadership styles and effective management

and ascertain which leadership style motivates employees to work better.

In an attempt to find answers to the research questions, the first hypothesis testing showed that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and employee performance. The second hypothesis testing also showed that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and accomplishment of organizational goals. Respondents positively responded in the third hypothesis, stating that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and effective management. Amongst the various leadership styles discussed in chapter two, the major leadership styles which are also known as the traditional styles are the authoritarian, democratic and the laissez faire leadership styles. Authoritarian leaders, also known as autocratic leaders, provide clear expectations for what needs to be done, when it should be done, and how it should be done. There is also a clear division between the leader and the followers. Authoritarian leaders make decisions independently with little or no input from the rest of the group. Authoritarian leadership is best applied to situations where there is little time for group decision-making or where the leader is the most knowledgeable member of the group. Participative leadership, also known as democratic leadership, is generally the most effective leadership style. Democratic leaders offer guidance to group members, but they also participate in the group and allow input from other group members. Participative leaders encourage group members to participate, but retain the final say over the decision-making process. Group members feel engaged in the process and are more motivated and creative. Delegative leaders offer little or no guidance to group members and leave decision-making up to group members. While this style can be effective in situations where group members are highly qualified in an area of expertise, it often leads to poorly defined roles and a lack of motivation.

The fourth objective which was to examine which leadership style motivates employees to work better was analyzed by determining the number of respondents that agreed to the statements representing each of the leadership styles.

Tables (26,27 and 28) in chapter four contain six statements each, which elaborate on the three leadership styles. These statements were represented on the questionnaires which were administered on respondents (see appendix). The tables also showed the degree to which respondents agreed and disagreed on each of the statements.

Table 29 showed that the leadership style with the highest percentage is the democratic leadership style. This table showed the total number of respondents that agreed to the statements representing the various leadership styles. According to these, 38.3% agreed to autocratic style, 44.2% agreed to the democratic style while only 17.5% agreed to the laissez faire leadership style. This showed that the laissez faire style is the least desirable leadership style while the democratic leadership style is most preferred by the respondents. This is illustrated graphically in figures (4.1) and (4.2). This implies that the respondents who are employees of Television Continental(TVC) prefer the democratic leadership style. Therefore, it can be inferred that the leadership style that motivates employees of TVC to work better is the democratic leadership style.

6. Conclusion

Effective management requires a good leadership style. Leadership styles, in managerial context, are the general ways a leader behaves towards subordinates in order to attain given objectives. The degree to which a manager delegates authority, the modes of power a manager employs and his relative concerns for human relationships or task orientation tend to reflect the manager's leadership style. Each organization is a unique combination of individuals, tasks and objectives. Each manager has a unique personality and set of abilities. Thus, leadership is not set of permanent qualities enabling one person to suit best all occasions. For a good leader in one situation may be worse in another. According to the findings of this research work, majority of the respondents believed more in the democratic leadership style. Conversely, it was also explained in chapter two that there is no best leadership style because different situations require different modes of leadership styles. There are a lot of arguments for and against each of the effective leadership styles. For example, the followers of an authoritarian leader are more prone to having low motivation and morale. They may find it difficult to get inspired because the leader is more impersonal, task oriented, demanding, and not considerate of their opinions. However, despite this, there are situations where an authoritarian leadership style is the most effective. Such as when time is short, when the leader has all the information, and a quick decision is needed. Anything other than an authoritarian leader will result in poorer outcomes. A charismatic leader can be very effective in inspiring his followers, but this may lead to the followers being dependent on the leader. Success may become reliant on the presence of the leader. A sudden absence of the leader can result in the possible collapse of the group.

With all these pros and cons, it is seen that there is no best leadership style and to be the best leader, you must be flexible. Leadership is a very significant functional area for the growth and development of an organization. A perfect leadership style of managers and supervisors brings a congenial organizational climate and helps to bring effectiveness. Most of the organizations attribute their success through effective leadership. Leaders gain credit by virtue of the competence they display in connection with the group task. Therefore, effective management in organizations requires a good understanding of the various leadership styles.

6.1. Recommendations Based on Findings

Leadership styles are essential ingredients of effective management in organizations. From the findings of this work, the democratic leadership style helps to motivate followers or subordinates in achieving organizational goals and objectives. However, other leadership styles are also necessary at different situations. Many leaders in organizations do not understand these and do not use the right leadership style when leading their subordinates. This could result in a lack of motivation of employees to perform better at work which would eventually lead to organizational ineffectiveness. Therefore, to address these anomalies of leadership styles in effective management, it is recommended that:

- Leadership should always be seen as a trust, which should be shouldered by only capable and credible people.
- Leaders should be made accountable for their stewardships through legislative or any possible means.
- Employees should be given training about leadership skills and how to manage subordinates effectively.
- Leaders should be flexible with their leadership styles so as to use the right leadership style when required

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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